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Mechatronic Design and Control of a Robotic System for Inspection Tasks

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Abstract. Mobile robots are being widely used in various security and inspection applications. This contribution describes a mechatronic design of a mobile robot with the function of inspection system in indoor environment. This robot is tele operated and can be remotely controlled by mobile phone or tablet. It is equipped by the so-called internal and external sensors, which are efficiently managed by the designed mechatronic control scheme. The development of a paradigmatic robotic system for inspection and security tasks is the main objective of this paper to demonstrate the feasibility of mechatronic solutions for inspection of indoor sites. The development of such systems will be exploited in the form of a tool-kit to be flexible and installed on a mobile system, in order to be used for inspection and monitoring, introducing high efficiency, quality and repetitiveness in the addressed sector. The interoperability of sensors with wireless communication constitutes a smart sensors tool-kit and a smart sensor network with powerful functions to be used efficiently for inspection purposes.

Keywords: Hybrid leg-wheel locomotion, Inspection, Interoperability, Low-cost monitoring, Experimental Tests.

1 Introduction

Inspection and home security robotics are becoming a reality in recent years. Moreover, the advent of robots is an intrinsic part of everyday life and has gained immense popularity in recent years [1-3]. Soft computing and artificial intelligence are successfully applied to machinery control, robot manipulation and engineering applications. With the integration of nonlinear system and communication technology, smart and secure industry and home is no longer an idea of science fiction. Therefore, a robot may play an important role in such environments. Indoor inspection, surveillance and home safety are becoming critical issues at this time to organizing a smart and secure place to live and/or work [4, 5].

Advances in Closed Circuit TV (CCTV) technology is turning video surveillance equipment into the most valuable loss prevention tool. Such technology is a safety and security tool, which has been made available for either industrial, commercial or residential applications. The use of surveillance systems can alert users for threatening situations worsen, as well as provide them with an important record of events, inspect part

of a production plant or inside an apartment for verification of structural and/or electrical components. However, in the conventional surveillance systems, only cameras and infrared cameras are used and their positions are fixed. As a result, a user may have problems viewing all video streams of cameras at the same time for tracking a moving object through a mobile device due to the object dynamics and limited network bandwidth. To solve these problems, devices have been developed for automatic inspection; these systems are equipped with sensors allowing the exploration of a building, as reported in [6]. Inspection and monitoring systems are only apparently tools easy to use and manage, in fact, they hide drawbacks such as high purchase and maintenance costs as well as significant financial commitment related to data management and processing. Those factors may greatly influence the wide spreading of those systems, in order to enhance the use of these technologies, new solutions have been explored dealing with the concept of robotic and automatic survey using low-cost technology [7]. More specifically, the use of a robotic platform may drastically reduce the time and cost needed for a relief, if compared to a classical approach. Moreover, the use of a low-cost technology both for the mechanical design of the mobile robot and the onboard sensors, allows the wide spreading of the robotic system and substitution in the case of damages, or if the robot is lost.

2 Requirements and solutions for the mechatronic design of surveillance and inspection robotic systems

The tasks of surveillance and automatic inspection need careful consideration to identify basic requirements and related solutions, as it is schematically represented in Fig. 1. First, basic requirements related to mobility issues deals with the site to inspect, i.e. buildings, industrial plants or any other indoor environment. They have in common to require a small sized mobile robot that can travel across a large variety of scenarios.

Mobile robots are usually classified according to the type of locomotion. Walking machines are well suited for unstructured environment because they can insure their stability in a wide range of situations, but they are mechanically complex and require high power and control efforts. On flat surfaces, they demonstrate their main limitation being low speed motion and high power consumption if compared with the other solutions [8]. Wheeled robots are the optimal solution for well-structured environment mainly flat and regular terrain. In off-road, their mobility is often very limited and highly depends on the type of environment and the dimension of the obstacles. Hybrid mobile robots combine advantages of both locomotion types, therefore in the recent past they are preferred for a large variety of scenarios and applications. According to the task and overall costs, three navigation modes are possible, pure tele-operation, safeguarded teleoperation, and autonomous navigation. The choice depends by the application and the environment. The sensorization is strictly related to the navigation type and the level of sophistication of the inspection. It is possible to classify internal and external sensors. The internal ones give the robot mobility control and navigation capabilities. They are proximity sensors, encoders, and GPS, accelerometers, gyroscopes, magnetic compasses, tilt and shock sensors. External sensors are related to the

specific task, for the inspection and surveillance sensors such as cameras, thermal cameras, laser, light, temperature, gas, smoke, oxygen, humidity, listening and ultrasound may be considered. Hardware and software reliability deals with the end-user/application of the robot. In fact, this issue has to be clarified at very early stage of the design since it is related to operation, maintenance, failure prevention. Last but not the least; communication tools are essential either for localization, navigation and data transmission. In addition to wired and wire-less communication, the new trend is the interoperability with any automatic and robotic system with other devices, such as home automation and security system in industrial plants according to industry 4.0.

Fig. 1. Flow-chart of the main requirements and solutions for a mechatronic design of inspection robotic systems

3 The mechatronic design of inspection robotic system for indoor applications

The mechatronic design of the inspection robotic system can be schematically made by two main parts; one is devote to the robot mobility and operation modes, and the other one is responsible to manage the external sensor suite, as shown in Fig. 2. According to the scheme reported in Fig. 2, (1) is the tablet or mobile phone used for the robot motion control and navigation by means of the two sliders represented in the zoomed view in (7), and the pro-gram is written with the DENSSION WIRC software. The USB WiFi router type TP-LINK Model TL-WN821N is (2) and allows the tablet to access and connect to the WIRC hardware. The webcam CAM (3) is the Logitech U0024 type. The DENSSION WIRC hardware (4) with four digital Inputs, four Digital Outputs and eight channels, is used to control the Servo Motors of the robot. The hardware in (4) is connected to and command the Arduino board (5), which drives via relay (6) the robot's actuators. The target (8) is displayed on the tablet or the mobile phone. The overall

mechatronic system architecture for the robot navigation is represented in (9). Therefore, when the robot in Fig. 3 moves in tele operated mode, the internal sensor suite is used to help the user to understand the environment and guide the robot to the path or close a place to inspect. In particular, (2) is an electronic board equipped with accelerometer, gravity and gyroscope sensors, GPS sensor, magnetic field and acceleration sensors. The front camera view for navigation is displayed as (3). External sensors are used for inspection and monitoring tasks. More specifically, in Fig. 3, (1) is the FLIR ThermaCAM S40 is the thermal infrared camera for videos, The 3D scan is the Xbox Kinect shown in (4), provided with an infrared sensor, and two additional micro cameras. An overview of possible industrial and non-industrial applications is reported in [9, 10]. The overall layout for the system is shown in Fig. 4, in which the main components may be recognized, mainly the robot in (2) with external and internal sensors, operating (3) and monitoring (5) (6) systems and power supply (6); (1) is the target. Figure 5 shows the control architecture to operate the robot and a representation of the interoperation with the equipment on-board.

Table 1 summarizes the main features of the proposed system. The integration of sensors and its management has been a subject of research activity in different specific domains [11-13]. An industrial network laboratory prototype has been proposed in [14] in which several kits have been implemented.

Figure 6 shows the robot operation during an indoor inspection. In particular, thermal detection of an electrical component is carried out. The interoperability of the sensors on board with navigation sensorization is managed by the control board and the WIRC Controller.

Fig. 2. Mechatronic architecture of the control for the THROO robot.

Fig. 3. Sensor installation on the inspection robot.

Fig. 4. Overview of the proposed mechatronic/robotic system.

Fig. 5. A scheme for the control architecture.

Table 1. System specifications.

Parameter description	Specification			
Robot system Hybrid mobile robot THROO	Size (LxHxW)	300(550)x140x400mm		
	Mass	4.5 kg no batteries		
	Max speed	Up to 0.5 m/s		
	Actuation	DC 24V 12 Nm 24 W		
	DOFs	2 (track) 1 (legs)		
	Max step size	100 mm		
Internal sensors		Range	Resolution	power
	PSH Accelerometer (Intel Inc.)	0...39.227	0.01 (0.024%)	0.006mA
	PSH Gyroscope sensor (Intel Inc.)	0...34.907	0.002 (0.005%)	6.1mA
	PSH Gravity sensor (Intel Inc.)	0...19.613	0.005 (0.024%)	0.006mA
	PSH Magn. field sensor (Intel Inc.)	0...800	0.5 (0.062%)	0.1mA
PSH Lin. Accel. sensor (Intel Inc.)	0...19.613	0.005 (0.024%)	0.006mA	
External sensors		Model		
	Thermal camera (FLIR)	ThermaCAM S40		
	Front camera (Logitech)	U0024 type		
3D scan (Xbox)	Kinect			
Communication	USB WiFi router	TP-LINK Model TL-WN821N		
Control station	No. monitors	2		
	No. computers/CPU	2		

Fig. 6. Photo sequence of an experimental test of data acquisition.

4 Conclusion

The mechatronic system and control proposed in this paper constitutes a solution for a broad range of scenarios spacing from home-security, inspection of industrial sites, brownfields, historical sites or sites dangerous or difficult to access by operators. First experimental tests are reported to show the engineering feasibility of the system and interoperability of the mobile hybrid robot equipped with sensors that allow real-time multiple acquisition and storage. The robot is equipped with external and internal sensors e.g., gyroscope, accelerometer, inclinometer, thermal camera, 3D motion capture system. First experimental results are reported in this paper.

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